

Designing Interactive Analytics Dashboards for Diverse Target Groups: The Process and Decision-making

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Abstract—This paper outlines the design process and rationale when designing data visualization and data analytics technology for different target groups. The objective is to document how design considerations, tailored to diverse sets of requirements and needs, influence the development of such technologies. We focus on two distinct use cases: one involving the design process tailored to the needs and preferences of practitioners, such as data analysts, and the other directed towards meeting the requirements of non-professional, volunteer-based participants from the general public engaged in participatory citizen science. In general, we observed diverse requirements and preferences concerning data visualization choices, additional functionalities, and analytical measures. These observations closely align with the specific goals of the tool and the expertise levels of its users.

Index Terms—visual analytics, interactive dashboards, digital tools, citizen science, technology design

I. INTRODUCTION

The majority of practices in the realm of technology development, and specifically the development of data visualization and analytics tools, often rely on a close collaboration with domain experts to allow for a continuous evaluation of usability of these tools and their integral features [1]. Specifically, a number of quantitative user studies are commonly being carried out to allow the domain experts to reflect, talk and learn about different data visualization and exploration techniques [2], [3]. However, at the core of these practices lies a common oversight where the design process prioritizes the needs and preferences of practitioners (e.g., data analysts), rather than the requirements of non-practitioners (e.g., the general public) [4]. Consequently, the resulting visualization tools may be too complex or may use a myriad of domain-specific technical terms that hinder comprehension and engagement among non-expert users.

This proves specifically problematic when such tools are used in participatory citizen science approaches that consider participation of non-professional, volunteer-based members of the general public [5]. Currently, the number of ongoing citizen science projects is on the constant rise, whereby the majority of these campaigns consider using some kind

of supporting digital technology, e.g., for data collection or validation during environmental or biodiversity monitoring. Although, digital tools are in principle meant to empower citizen scientists, their effectiveness hinges on factors such as usability and accessibility. As mentioned at the outset, this is due to the design process that only caters to rather narrow user demographics, which leads to such tools often being incomprehensible to a broader spectrum of the non-professionals.

In an effort to remedy these issues, this contribution documents two distinct design and decision-making processes and the related considerations when developing interactive data analytics dashboards for different target groups. On one hand side, we focus on the specific needs and requirements of a wide range of participants who possess limited or no prior analytical knowledge. These groups of participants are presently undergoing orientation and training to participate in environmental data collection campaigns. This part of the discussion outlines the ongoing research efforts within the GREENGAGE project funded under the Horizon Europe framework [6]. On the other hand, we focus on preferences and desires of domain experts that summarize the findings from continuous conceptualization and reflection sessions that are carried out at our research institution.

II. DESIGN PROCESS FOR THE NON-PRACTITIONERS

A. Background

As part of the GREENGAGE project [6], various digital tools (portable sensors, mobile apps, web-based platforms) are utilized to facilitate active engagement from the general public in observing, sensing, and monitoring their urban environments. These meticulous data collection campaigns target five pilots spread across five distinct European cities and regions (Copenhagen, Turano, Gerace, Bristol and North-Brabant). The selection of digital tools is driven by the specific information requirements of each pilot, aimed at understand-

ing and tackling diverse environmental issues affecting their respective communities.

One of the concerned tools (Figure 1) relates to the interactive data analytics dashboard developed at our research institution. The dashboard is an interactive web-based platform that allows users to inspect and monitor the quality of the collected environmental time-series data (e.g., air quality, noise). The dashboard also offers a variety of visual cues and metrics for data exploration and analysis (see Figure 1).

B. Design Process and Decisions

The design process of the dashboard and its integral features was guided by a set of requirements drafted from a number of intra-consortia collaborative sessions that took place within the so-called Pilot Support Teams (PSTs). PSTs are responsible for assisting in the development of localized roadmaps for the pilots and executing the planned monitoring campaigns through the understanding of the unique situational contexts within each locality. PSTs consist of dedicated consortium members that represent both the technical (i.e., technology providers) and non-technical domains (i.e., participatory and social sciences) who are continuously supporting the pilot owners. These sessions served as a creative space of deliberation for the pilot owners, who acted as representatives of their communities. The sessions facilitated collaborative brainstorming to address the multifaceted local challenges at hand and determine the desired graphical representations of supporting data.

By engaging in a continuous dialogue with the pilot owners, we have gained valuable insights into diverse needs and preferences of the end-users across various pilot locations. We have identified the need for an intuitive design that facilitates effortless navigation and comprehension. This stressed the necessity for a user-friendly interface and simplified functionalities, whereby the tool should also prioritize accessibility. Thus, we have selected a comprehensive single-page dashboard layout without any scrolling options. Additionally, we have incorporated clear labels and inclusive color schemes to accommodate individuals who may have visual impairments (e.g., color blindness). The dashboard is equally limited to visualizing only one time-series at a time, to prevent visual clutter and maintain clarity of data visualization.

Looking at the supporting visual elements, we have identified the need for simple representations that provide an intuitive way to understand complex information. For instance, an interactive map was deemed to be the most suitable for displaying geospatial data, specifically the individual data collection localities.

A basic line chart would provide a general overview of the acquired data with instantaneous depiction of temporal evolution of a variable. In general, line charts allow users to discern general trends and identify potential outliers. To make the chart even more intuitive, we have implemented color markings (i.e., vertical blue bars) to depict the existing temporal gaps, which may appear as a singular occurrence or a continuous sequence of missing data points. Both features will allow users

to identify potential data faults at a glance. Additionally, we have integrated a range slider beneath the primary line chart, enabling seamless navigation and continuous monitoring of the dataset's selected timeframe.

We have also implemented a histogram to display the distribution characteristics of continuous data and to help users identify a general tendency towards a certain value or a range. Based on our prior study [7], we have chosen a specific interval division with an adequate number of bins to preserve the distribution while preventing overplotting of intervals. After the user selects a range of extreme values that could potentially be outliers, the system instantly highlights them as red marks on a line chart.

One of the additional requirements was to consider a heatmap view to allow for visualizing time-based patterns in acquired data. We have decided to aggregate the data on hourly and daily bases to meet the anticipated analytical requirements of the pilots arising from specific use cases, such as mobility modes or pattern analysis, air quality and noise pollution. We have equally highlighted the missing values in a vibrant manner, as it was done in the case of the line chart.

Additionally, we have incorporated easily comprehensible data quality metrics, such as completeness, accuracy and consistency. These are presented as pie charts to display numerical proportions, indicating the extent to which the 100% threshold has been achieved. In addition to visualizations, including a data table with column overview would offer users the ability to explore specific data points and their respective values.

III. DESIGN PROCESS FOR THE PRACTITIONERS

A. Background

As a research company, we strive to continuously refine and enhance our developed tools through a tight collaboration with our industry partners. By leveraging their expertise and through insight into their daily practices, we are making sure that our solutions are meeting the evolving needs and expectations of our end users and stakeholders.

B. Design Process and Decisions

In this context, the design process relies on continuous conceptualization and evaluation sessions conducted between the domain experts and the dashboard designers. The initial stage of the design process involves a collaborative analysis of common data analytics workflows, specific data-related tasks and typical daily practices by both domain experts and dashboard designers. The aim is to identify recurring tasks and determine the optimal methods to address them effectively. Once these are identified, dashboard designers proceed with conceptualization of a dashboard prototype (see Figure 2).

While the general needs of non-practitioners call for simplified functionalities, the practitioners require a more sophisticated design. The solution should prioritize aspects such as responsiveness, flexibility and customization, making the tool easily adaptable to a common workflow of domain experts. This entails a variety of advanced data visualization options (further informed by renowned guiding principles for

Fig. 1. Web-based data analytics dashboard developed for the non-practitioners used to analyse and monitor data quality through visual cues, quality metrics, and statistics, allowing users to quickly identify potential issues.

Fig. 2. Web-based data analytics dashboard developed for the practitioners with advanced and responsive visualization and customization options.

effective visualization [8]), interactive filtering and drill-down functionalities, advanced data manipulation and transformation options within a flexible multi-panel dashboard structure (see Figure 2). The flexibility of the dashboard is enhanced by allowing users to freely reposition individual visualization panels (see Figure 3) to adapt to their workflow needs and to align with their analytical sense-making process [9].

The dashboard prototype is equally capable of handling and displaying complex multivariable datasets, whereby more time-series may be visualized at the same time allowing a comparative assessment across the entire dataset. These are simultaneously depicted in a number of tailored visualization

panels: a line chart with a range slider, a histogram, a boxplot, duration curves plot, and a calendar heatmap. Additionally, a data table and descriptive statistics table allow inspection of raw data values and further support hierarchical sorting of the variables.

IV. FUTURE STEPS

In the current phase of the research, the evaluation of these solutions has not yet been initiated. However, a continuous evaluation of usability and functionality is essential for the refinement of the tools and has already been planned for the coming months. For non-practitioners, this will occur during

Fig. 3. An example of repositioning the core visualization panels within the data analytics dashboard to align with a user-centred workflow needs.

dedicated virtual training sessions within the piloting phase, where members of the general public will be instructed in the use of the tools. We will gather the feedback from the process of familiarization with the features and address any challenges encountered during the use of the tools. For practitioners, the evaluation will take place within a number of workshops with a limited number of participants, where experts will present a real-world domain problem as a case study and evaluate the usability of the developed dashboard. This process will be closely monitored and any potential challenges will be addressed in the subsequent developmental phase.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have documented the design process for designing digital technology tailored to individuals with varying levels of technical proficiency and familiarity with analytical concepts. Specifically, we examined the preferences and expectations of both non-practitioners and domain experts to inform the design of an interactive data analytics dashboard. Overall, we noticed varying needs and preferences in both data visualization options, supporting features and analytical metrics, closely reflecting the tool's purpose and the users' knowledge levels. Specifically, the design specifications for non-practitioners comprised an intuitive interface with simplified functionalities, emphasizing accessibility, featuring a single-page dashboard layout, clear labeling, inclusive color schemes, and limiting visual clutter. In contrast, practitioners' design requirements prioritize responsiveness, flexibility, and customization, incorporating advanced data visualization options, interactive filtering, drill-down functionalities, and advanced data manipulation within a multi-panel dashboard structure.

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